

Closing the Loop: A Global Synthesis of Learning Analytics in Continuous Assessment

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Abstract. Learning Analytics has become a major topic in the education sector, and it can be used to improve various aspects of education. This paper presents a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) examining the application of Learning Analytics (LA) to enhance the design and implementation of Continuous Assessments (CA) and Continuous Assessment Modules in Higher Education. In this process, 44 articles were reviewed. Findings indicate that LA can be effectively implemented alongside Learning Management Systems (LMS) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) to enhance Continuous Assessment Modules, yielding benefits such as identifying at-risk students, improving student performance, and enabling adaptable assessments. The results show that implementing a Continuous Assessment Module using LA can increase student performance, help identify at-risk students, and enable the implementation of corrective measures where needed. Recommendations include conducting a study comparing the implementation of a Continuous Assessment Module using LA with that of a typical module within a higher education institution.

Keywords: Continuous Assessment, Higher Education, Learning Analytics, Student Performance

1 Introduction

With Learning Analytics (LA) becoming a significant topic [1] in higher education over the last decade, the question is how LA can enhance the design and structure of Continuous Assessment Modules. Over the past decade, LA has begun to play an increasingly important role in shaping how higher education institutions implement Continuous Assessment Modules for students, with the aim of improving student learning and performance. According to Al-Baity, Alsaed [2], implementing Continuous Assessment (CA) relies on the data system used while LA enables educational institutions to better understand how to use data to facilitate continuous, efficient improvement.

Universities often employ tools and techniques to enhance their students' performance and ensure that learning occurs efficiently and effectively [3]. As Big Data is increasingly used, LA has become a valuable tool, helping discover hidden patterns and commonalities and analyse outcomes in educational datasets to inform relevant actions [4]. Caspari-Sadeghi [4] states that there are three main types of analytics used in higher education to understand and improve processes and outcomes in educational environments, one of which is LA.

Higher education institutions employ various types of assessments, but the two primary types are formative and summative assessments. The frequency and stakes of these assessments also affect student performance; some institutions and modules are considering implementing CA [5]. The frequency of assessments refers to how often they occur, and the stakes of assessments refer to how heavily each assessment contributes to the final mark [5]. LA can be utilised to improve the design and implementation of Continuous Assessment Modules in higher education; however, if not implemented correctly, it could undermine these improvements [6]. LA is relevant to enhancing higher education as technology has evolved, enabling everything around us to be data-driven [4]. The correct use of LA should aid in the design and development of Continuous Assessment Modules, as it leverages existing data to identify trends and inform potential solutions to enhance them. Continuous Assessment Modules are a new approach that higher education institutions implement to aid student performance and learning [7]. CA is relevant as it can be classified as both formative and summative assessment. Students often link CAs with a motivation to learn consistently as feedback is provided, depending on how the CA is set up [6].

Therefore, the research question this paper addresses is *how LA can enhance the design and implementation of Continuous Assessment Modules in higher education*.

Section 2 reviews the history of LA and CA in higher education, followed by the research methodology in Section 3. Section 4 presents the findings, which Section 5 analyses to inform improvements to CA design. The paper concludes with recommendations for future research.

2 Literature background

2.1 Assessments and Types of Assessments

Assessment is an integral part of learning and teaching [8]. It is no longer just recognised as a tool for measuring learning, but as a process that supports and shapes educational practices/methods [8], and should be designed to help students learn and engage with their work [7]. Two common types of assessments in higher education are formative and summative. Formative assessments periodically evaluate what students know and can do, whereas summative assessments measure students' cumulative knowledge of the specific module [9].

2.2 Continuous Assessment

CA is when students are continually assessed throughout the academic period and is often viewed as formative than summative assessments [7]. Having formative assessments as a CA allows students multiple chances to develop their knowledge and provides constructive feedback, which can be used in later assessments [10, 11] while improving student motivation [6]. The type of CAs depends on the institution and how it chooses to implement them. A common way of executing CAs is through online platforms, also known as Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs). Holmes [7] noted that the use of online assessments has positively impacted students' motivation and engagement. Continuous Assessment Modules can be seen as a module consisting out of CAs as the assessment type.

2.3 Challenge associated with assessment

A challenge in assessments is that lecturers often confuse formative and summative assessments. Taras, Molina [8] identified a discrepancy in lecturers' understanding of formative and summative assessments in their study. In addition, formative assessments are seen as 'good', whereas summative assessments are seen as 'bad' [13]. Due to this perception, well-designed summative assessments could positively affect students [13], but there is sometimes an overreliance on summative tasks [12]. It is important for educators to use both formative and summative assessment types to support students' learning and development [12-14].

2.4 Learning Analytics as a Tool to Improve Continuous Assessment (CA)

The Society for Learning Analytics Research (SoLAR), founded in 2011, is devoted to "improving teaching and learning by analytics as well as promoting the collaboration and publication of Learning Analytics research" [1]. LA is defined as "the measurement, collection, analysis and reporting of data about learners and their contexts for purposes of understanding and optimising learning and the environments in which it occurs" [4]. Higher Education commonly uses LA to see how students are performing, identify areas for improvement, determine where most students are struggling, and determine which teaching methods and assessments are most beneficial for students. When using LA, specifically Predictive Learning Analytics (PLA), Herodotou, Rienties [15] noted that when 'at-risk' students are identified, appropriate measures can be implemented early, such as notifying the student and lecturer, allowing lecturers to take corrective action.

LA can be used as a tool to improve CA by gathering relevant data on students' learning progress [9], monitoring student engagement, predicting students' performance [16], and evaluating the impact of learning being done [7].

3 Methodology

In this article, the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach is employed as the research method. A formal and systematic approach is followed, such as identifying the research question, searching all relevant articles/studies, selecting and evaluating published articles, applying selection criteria, extracting the data, and using the extracted data to answer the research question [17, 18]

In this research paper, three databases were primarily used to retrieve relevant articles: Scopus, Web of Science, and ProQuest. To get relevant articles, the following general search string was used: (*"Learning Analytics" AND "higher education" AND "Continuous Assessment"*) OR (*"Learning Analytics" AND "student performance" AND "higher education"*) OR (*"Learning Analytics" AND "formative assessment" AND "summative assessment"*) OR (*"Learning Analytics" AND "assessment design" AND "higher education"*). The inclusion criteria are peer-reviewed articles, journal articles, or conference papers in English published since 2011, when the Society for Learning Analytics Research was established. During Screening, the exclusion criteria removed articles, journal articles, or conference papers that were inaccessible or had little relevance to the connection between LA and CA.

In Figure 1, the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) flowchart illustrates how the studies retrieved from the search were screened and selected, resulting in the identification of the final 44 articles used in this study.

Fig. 1. PRISMA Flowchart

Selected studies were extracted using a bibliometric data matrix that included the relevant details such as the Author, whether it's a journal or a conference, the Journal/Conference Title, date, country of study, keywords, and abstract.

4 Data analysis

After extracting all relevant information from the studies, the data were analysed, and key findings were documented.

Figure 2 shows the number of publications from 2011 to 2025. The number of articles is low from 2011 to 2018, but it increases from 2019 to 2025. This is understandable, as the Society for Learning Analytics Research (SOLAR) was only founded in 2011, and the first issue of the Journal of Learning Analytics was published in 2014 [1]. The hybrid education model saw a spike in interest from 2020 to 2022 due to COVID-19. Based on these timeframes, from 2011 to 2016 (3 articles), LA and LMS integration was introduced. From 2016 to 2018 (5 articles), early LA platforms and predictive modelling were expanded. From 2019 to 2025 (36 articles), there was an explosion regarding AI-integration, LA, and student learning personalisation.

In Figure 3, the countries with the most published articles are the United Kingdom and the United States of America. One reason the United Kingdom and the United States of America have more published articles is that they are more advanced and developed than many other countries. However, research on LA is spreading across many countries, indicating increased global awareness of LA.

Fig. 2. Articles published per year

Fig. 3. Geo chart of countries and articles

From the articles, three main themes emerged, which will be discussed in detail: Learning Analytics, Assessments, and student performance.

5 Findings

5.1 Learning Analytics (LA)

For Learning Analytics, subthemes identified were the use of LA, Learning management systems, AI, and data management. These will now be discussed.

Caspari-Sadeghi [4] defines LA as the way data, regarding learners and their work, is measured, collected, analysed, and reported, while Russell, Smith [19] state that the primary purpose of LA is to understand the relationship between students' engagement and performance. LA can be implemented with the aid of Artificial Intelligence (AI). Alotaibi [20] reports that implementing LA with AI agents in an LMS enhanced student engagement and learning, providing personalised support that empowered students during the blended-learning phase of the COVID-19 pandemic. When AI is integrated into an LMS for personalised learning and LA, at-risk students are identified early enough for lecturers to take corrective actions and provide data-driven insights, thereby enhancing student learning and education [20]. Furthermore, Sahni [21] states that, with the correct use of LA plugins in an LMS and interventions, instructors observed increases in online interaction and student performance. It is noted that within an LMS, Student Performance Indicators can be used to enable continuous monitoring of student progress, which can aid in identifying 'at-risk' students and providing feedback based on their results [22]

Learning Analytic Dashboards (LAD) are becoming increasingly popular as a tool that provides visualisation of students' activity and performance in comparison to their peers [23]. LADs allow lecturers to view and analyse students' individual performance and the course's performance, as they combine data from Learning Management Systems with LA to present informative Analytics Dashboards that present information for lecturers to view visually. LADs can also be seen as helpful for students, as dashboard access and use had a positive effect on students' performance, as students could realise that they don't spend enough time in their course through low interaction displayed in the dashboard [24]. Functionality that can be added to LADs for students includes, but is not limited to, statistical, textual, and visual feedback, as well as the ability to compare grades with peers, which improves e-learning effectiveness [25].

LA comes with its challenges, with a major challenge being student privacy [21]. A large number of stakeholders and students believe that ethics and privacy are important aspects to cover within LA [26] while there were students who expressed concern and uneasiness about using LA and data profiles being set up [27]. In terms of ethics and privacy, the primary concerns are whether informed consent is obtained, whether data is protected, and what the protocol for sharing data with external parties is [26].

5.2 Assessments

The subthemes for assessment identified include assessment in general, CA, Formative Assessment, and Summative Assessment.

Assessments measure learning and support and shape educational practices [8]. Lau [13] states that formative or summative are equally important and should be connected. CAs are often seen more as a formative assessment than as a summative assessment [7] where formative assessments focus more on the process [8]. Formative Assessments add value to the learning process by providing feedback that helps students grow and perform better, while recognizing and preventing mistakes [28]. It is essential that feedback be given promptly. Afzaal, Zia [29] discussed the use of explainable AI to compute data-driven feedback and generate actionable results that support student self-learning.

In contrast, summative assessment focuses more on the product. Johansson, Kanapathippillai [10] note that the key factors in continuous formative assessment are reputation and practice, but individual feedback also plays a vital role. It has been reported that continuous formative assessment positively impacts students' learning performance by providing feedback that helps them identify areas of knowledge gaps and areas for improvement [10]. Participants find it important to have integrated formative and summative feedback regarding their progress [30]. CA not only helps improve student performance but also supports student learning through feedback and increases student motivation [6].

An aspect not covered in many articles is Learning Design (LD). Divjak, Barthakur [31] elaborate on how LA starts with LD, defining LD as the sequence of teaching and learning activities, along with the associated resources and student support. They further elaborate that when implementing a continuous improvement cycle in a course, one has to start with LD, which is crucial to ensure that well-defined learning outcomes are established [32] and that assessments are well aligned with those outcomes. Alignment between learning outcomes and assessments is known as constructive alignment, which ensures the validity of an evaluation, and the choice of method for applying and prioritising learning outcomes strongly relies on the teaching-learning context [31, 33]. Formative assessment is a continuous evaluation process that provides meaningful feedback to both students and educators. This feedback enables teachers to adjust current and future learning outcomes, refine instructional content, and better support student learning trajectories [31].

5.3 Student Performance

The subthemes for the last theme include at-risk students, student performance, and student motivation and dedication.

Fernández-Olaskoaga, Catasús [34] explore how big data techniques can aid in predicting student performance, detecting at-risk students, data visualisation, and intelligent feedback. When predicting student performance, predictors can include percentage of grades up to a certain date, LMS activity compared to other students, prior academic history, and student characteristics [35]. When identifying at-risk students, Predictive Learning Analytics (PLA) can help assist students who may not pass the specific course or are struggling academically [15]. They further state that PLA applications, such as Course Signal, not only identify at-risk students but also send warning messages and feedback to lecturers and students.

Kustitskaya, Esin [36] discuss an approach to improve student retention by identifying 'at-risk' students through forecasting academic success using academic history, LMS activity, and current academic history to determine whether a student is on the path to success. If not, corrective measures can be implemented. In addition to current academic data, predictive analytics uses historical student records, high school grades, parents' education, and other learning environments to identify at-risk students [37]. The use of LA systems enables lecturers/teachers to enhance and facilitate learning [15]. Benefits for teachers/lecturers when incorporating LA include continuous student monitoring, improved teaching strategies, and more efficient interventions [38]. Other non-academic factors may also contribute to a lack in student performance, such as family issues, lack of time management, adapting to a new social environment, hunger and poverty, prior learning experience, and cultural-ethnicity [19, 39, 40]. These should be considered when making predictions. When linking student motivation to formative assessment, formative assessments strongly influence student motivation by encouraging interest and commitment and challenging students [41].

Ifenthaler, Schumacher [42] introduce another perspective, noting that students often use self-assessment to achieve higher grades and improve their performance, suggesting that higher education institutions should support self-assessment to facilitate better learning and potentially enhance student performance.

5.4 Challenges faced when implementing Learning Analytics

While LA can be beneficial, it does come with challenges. A significant concern when using LA is privacy and ethical issues [43], as students have the right to be notified that data is being collected and to know which data is being used for what purpose [4]. Students have expressed discomfort because they don't know how higher education institutions protect their data [27] or who would have access to it, as students prefer that only those related to the course have such information [44]. Students need to consent before their data is used in LMSs and LA to allow for transparency and privacy [45]. When higher institutions work with learners' data, they must provide students with a reason to believe that their information will not be disclosed or used and ensure that students are aware of how their data is being processed [27].

Another challenge regarding adopting LA is the use of technology. The technology infrastructure used to implement LA plays a vital role; without it, implementation is

adversely affected [26]. In less developed or developing countries such as Afghanistan and Egypt, there is a gap in ICT use and awareness, as many students lack ICT knowledge [46].

Resistance or unwillingness to adopt LA is another challenge to its adoption [47]. Reasons for reluctance include taking risks or making changes, a lack of competence in incorporating tools, and a lack of understanding of how LA works [4]. Herodotou, Maguire [47] state that, although there is resistance to adopting LA, teachers report that tools like PLA are easy to use and helpful, yet PLA tools remain underused.

6 Discussion

The LA Cycle by Doug Clow is used as a framework to construct a conceptual model to map the findings. In Doug Clow's Learning Analytics cycle, there are four phases, namely learners, data, metric, and intervention [48].

The first phase of this cycle is learners. Learners will continue to engage in their usual learning activities, including studying and taking assessments. The second phase, data, involves generating and capturing learner data, including demographic and academic information obtained through a Learning Management System (LMS). The third phase, metrics, involves processing the data into analytics to give insight into the learning process. The last phase, interventions, takes the metrics from the previous phase and implements necessary changes or improvements into the learning system. By cycling through each of these places, a continuous feedback loop is created that improves student learning and performance. The findings indicated that this model should be adapted to address the ethical and privacy challenges associated with student data. Each phase will now be discussed in more detail.

6.1 Consent/Acknowledgement

As ethics and privacy have been perceived as significant challenges in LA, an approach needs to be established to address this issue and enable the smooth use of LA. Students have the right to be informed about how their data is used and for what purpose [4]. Therefore, Higher Education Institutions need to inform students at enrolment about the use of their data with LA. The students should be briefed on the data that will be collected, analysed, and used to inform future improvements to the course and students. Students are uncomfortable with not knowing who will have access to this data [27]; hence, it is important for students to be informed about which stakeholders and tools will have access to their data.

6.2 Learners

In the context of the Continuous Assessment Modules, learner engagement plays a significant role. CAs increase student motivation and engagement through frequent feedback [6]. Since formative assessment can be conducted continuously throughout the learning process, it can be used to implement a Continuous Assessment Module [31]. When students work within an LMS, their actions will be tracked and interpreted in the next phase [21]. The most important aspect is that the cycle begins before the

assessments take place, it starts with assessment preparation, class attendance, and online engagement [49]. In this paper, assessments are the most significant factor, as meaningful assessments are essential for reporting student progress and for supporting and steering students' learning [31]. It is also noted that formative assessments can aid in collecting data to improve student learning, while summative assessments can aid in collecting data to assess whether students have retained knowledge after completing specific learning materials [31].

6.3 Data

The third phase involves collecting data regarding students from the previous phase [48]. This data includes the student's assessment results, their engagement with the content and the course, and other related data that can be interpreted. Data is captured using an LMS integrated with AI-based tools/agents. Within the LA area, the primary goal is to identify at-risk students [50], data extracted from the LMS used, which contains student interactions and progress within the course. The use of LA, integrated with AI in LMS, can enhance the quality and accessibility of data, allowing for the generation of more comprehensive reports on students' activity [20].

6.4 Metrics

Within the Metrics phase, data collected from the previous phase is processed, analysed, and interpreted [48]. This is where LA comes into full effect by applying the analytical techniques and applications, such as PLA, to predict students' performance, identify 'at-risk' students to be able to assist them [50], and to answer crucial questions from the data provided in the previous phase. Other key metrics include performance trends, engagement metrics, and assessment effectiveness.

6.5 Intervention

The final phase of the cycle, intervention, involves corrective measures informed by the metrics from the previous phase to determine the next step. This includes targeted feedback for specific students, personalised learning resources, early-warning alerts for at-risk students, and ongoing adjustments to the structure of the Continuous Assessment Module [21]. This aspect is important for identifying at-risk students, as lecturers can take corrective measures as soon as they identify students struggling academically. Lecturers can assist these students by providing constructive feedback to help them get back on track [51]. Giving feedback directly to students increases students' self-awareness and promotes student engagement, a crucial aspect of self-regulated learning [19].

6.6 Repetition of the cycle

Although the element of repetition of the cycle is not a 'phase' of this cycle, it is important to apply this cycle continuously within a Continuous Assessment Module. A Continuous Assessment Module features ongoing assessments throughout the course, allowing data to be captured after learners complete each one. Using LA and AI agents, data is interpreted, and corrective measures are taken before the following assessment

is conducted. This can also aid in improving the module's design and in recognising at-risk students at the earliest stage.

Cycling through these stages ensures a feedback loop that uplifts learning outcomes. Simultaneously, the model adapts to current LA challenges by prioritizing data ethics and privacy.

Fig. 4. Adapted Learning Analytics Cycle

Figure 4 shows that this cycle continuously goes through all the phases. This conceptual model was used to map the findings, as it demonstrates how LA can enhance the design and implementation of Continuous Assessment Modules in higher education.

7 Conclusion

Using an SLR approach to examine the relationship between LA and the Continuous Assessment Module, this paper explores how LA can aid in the design and implementation of such modules.

This paper presents a refined conceptual model that integrates Learning Analytics (LA) into Continuous Assessment design, illustrating how iterative data-driven feedback loops can improve student performance and engagement. By incorporating ethical considerations and AI-enabled LMS tools, it offers a practical framework for identifying at-risk learners and implementing timely, personalized interventions within higher education.

Limitations of this research paper include the lack of published articles on CAs and Continuous Assessment Modules, and the low number of articles published in South Africa on the use of LA in CAs. A recommendation for future research is to apply this framework in an empirical study of LA in CAs, within a higher education setting.

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